

Multilateral Impact of Coronavirus on Society

Actual Effects and Prognostics

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ABSTRACT: Our present is being defined by one of the biggest crisis this century has seen. The COVID-19 outbreak has spread around the globe damaging the health system and producing fatalities, hitting indirectly on all aspects of life as we know it, creating a vicious cycle with probable long term side effects even in the aftermath of the event. With all modern technology and knowledge, it seems that society is still fragile in the face of biology and nature. In this article, we analyze the aspects and domains of society during the present coronavirus pandemics describing the rupture within the bio-psycho-social balance and the actual effects and perspectives of this phenomenon on limited and general scale. It is clear that life, as we know it, has reached a point of drastic change, from the aspect of individual human life to the aspects of social function because health, economy, psychology, environment, technology and all interconnected elements of modern living are fluctuating in different levels changing the status of well-being as we know it.

KEYWORDS: coronavirus, balance, society, perspectives, pandemics

Introduction

An unexpected health crisis hit the world in the end of 2019. With all modern, sophisticated technology and new discoveries in medicine, it still seems that we are helpless in front of nature's sometimes twisted biology. Fear of the unknown, the mass anxiety, panic and confusion were amplified by the strict and severe protocols of prevention. The novel coronavirus has a very high rate of infectiousness, and prevention of treatment is still in study progress. Facing with a powerful, invisible enemy is one of the greatest challenges of this century and drastic measures are necessary but, society was not prepared for this kind of situation and the present impact will still have echoes in the aftermath of the pandemic.

The consequences of the pandemics are still to be uncovered and the main questions are related to how will life be after this situation, what is the long term impact on the life standard, what changes this will bring on the collective and individual well-being, life-satisfaction and interpersonal relations. And after answering these questions there is a massive unknown related to the economic impact that is already affecting society at all levels bringing new problems into the general population well-being (Chakraborty and Maity 2020, 138882).

Immediate impact on society

A first dramatic change was on the normal way of life by sudden changing of the interpersonal relations but also in the relation of the every individual with himself. As an objective in preventing and slowing the spread of the virus, social distancing was the new way of living (Verma and Prakash 2020, 7352-7363). Social distancing has various meanings – isolation during the emergency state, quarantine, circulation restrictions and keeping 2 m distancing while in public. Basically, life as it is known became a continuous defence mechanism. Isolation transitioned from physical to psychological, repressing problems to the self of the individual. Isolation for people who live alone is even worse as their relationships are disrupted completely. Until one point, increasing home activity seems a good idea but after a time, the lack of professional and recreational routines will add more weight on the psychology of people (Hsiang, Allen, Annan-Phan, Bell, Bolliger, Chong and Lau 2020, 262-267).

Risking contacting the virus and the severe prevention propaganda made people accept restrictions to preserve life, in order to protect their health. But human life is by definition social, with interactions, and group activities. Society by its definition is a system constructed by the idea of group and community efforts. So consequences can be important from the individual to the entire construction of society. Moreover, effects of this disconnection will start waves of repercussions over mental health, law, society organisation and economy. Loss of income, unemployment will reflect into community as social inequity, law problems increasing, poverty, and social systems losing balance at all levels (Ali and Alharbi 2020, 138861).

The quality of life

Quality of life is a complex concept. It cannot be defined on scientific an objective criteria but it can be assessed with subjective principles by measuring satisfactory principles at individual and group level. There are few common elements between scientific sociology principles on life quality, the medical idea and the collective impression. The difference between groups come from the specific interests. For example, medical community analyse medical criteria, sociology analyse well-being as a complex of material and immaterial data and individual or group quality of life is measured by all markers at all levels of life – profession, family, relationships, financial status (Singh and Singh 2020, 2).

The coronavirus crisis modified the criteria of well-being, focusing it on health, prevention from getting infected and keeping the family and surroundings safe. As stated, every level of life quality as structure, orientation, priorities, have been modified. The most terrifying idea in society is the rising uncertainty of an already uncertain future because even the most modern and advanced communities have no idea about the consequences that this pandemic will have over society (Elavarasan and Pugazhendhi 2020, 138858).

Severe restrictions have impacted lifestyle so much that there is almost a new idea of civilisation. Limitation and isolation have conducted to developing new criteria for satisfactory life: home work conditions, limited travels, focusing on the house and family well-being, creating a safe environment both physical and psychological. At this point, there can be advantages because, as social and professional recreational activities are limited, people are forced to face and solve in order to have a comfortable surroundings (Torales, O'Higgins, Castaldelli-Maia and Ventriglio, 2020).

Limiting economy will reflect on a new financial attitude. Decreasing incomes or job loss and reduction of opportunities for recreational activities (travel, shopping, and restaurants) will lead to a new orientation on spending resources with refocusing on interests and activities in non-economic areas (Van Bavel, Baicker, Boggio, Capraro, Cichocka, Cikara and Drury 2020, 1-12).

In normal life situations, the individual is focused on his well-being in the middle of community, using all aspects of society and opportunities to raise his life quality. The coronavirus crisis has created a new paradox: public interest and public responsibility are overcoming the individualism. Disruption of the entire social matrix, are taking away the elements that people rely on to conduct a good life. In order to regain those elements, a group effort is necessary (Guan, Deng and Zhou 2020). Collective responsibility is the motto of this time not only to prevent the spread of the health problem but also to a fast recovery of the lost balance. We could describe this situation as a *quid quo pro* state. Society and collective work is important for an individual well-being so a disruption in that matrix will force the individual to solidarity and team effort in order to rebuild satisfactory life networks (Mogi and Spijker, 2020).

Society changing and collective efforts are decreasing globalism and are rising the interest for national interest. Patriotism and the country economical and health well-being are cited as well as on the political stage but also on every society level. Moreover, the relationship between state and citizen has changed. Social state has thinned drastic with tendency to be more an administrative core as the public view is that now, the state is not interested in its citizens and their

life quality (Dryhurst, Schneider, Kerr, Freeman, Recchia, Van Der Bles and van der Linden 2020, 1-13). So, national interest should go beyond politics and be about saving and supporting the people. It is a relative sensitive problem because, as we look into history, crises tend to make way for drastic measures and fear and low life quality tend to be perfect conditions for extremist and ultra-nationalism ideas. It is collective fear and poverty that allows people to believe that only extreme measures can save them without realising what they are giving up (Malecki, Keating and Safdar 2020).

Public health impact

The coronavirus outbreak took health institutions by surprise and even the most advanced health systems could not face this threat with maximum potential. The problem for society does not reside in the immediate risks of this virus. With all efforts being concentrated into making protocols and treatments for the management of the situation, the other aspects of medicine are left on a second plan. It is a fact that even modern medicine and medical infrastructure could not deal with the virus and with the other health problems and all health branches were focused on the epidemics leaving other diseases with less attention. Mortality and morbidity for other health problems not associated with Covid-19 are increasing and social impact could be important as well for professional and economical levels (Slobodin and Cohen 2020, 470).

Law and crime

Job loss, financial problems and reducing life satisfaction can lead to a rise of criminality. We are not speaking only about theft, drugs, and other known illicit activities. There are worries that the situation that coronavirus has produces will generate new law problems as some people will try to profit from the situation. An example could be the promotion and commercialising of fake treatments, prevention drugs and vaccines against the novel virus. Financial incomes provided with false beliefs and people's fear is a very serious threat to society and public health as some of these false products could lead to health side effects as well as financial and law problems (Rudolph and Zacher 2020). On the other hand, emergency state has deep law reinforcement and there are people who neglect and disobey rules related to the social distancing and health protocols. Not respecting prevention rules or not declaring symptoms are some of the problems. Interfere in the medical and epidemiological process during crisis is not only harmful for community and health personnel but it is now introduced as a criminal offence with legally implications (Qiu, Shen, Zhao, Wang, Xie and Xu 2020, 33). The persons who disregarded and did not respect the measures ordered by the Romanian authorities, especially the measures of quarantine and isolation at home (and who continue to do so), committed the crime of Thwarting disease control (Hegheş 2020, 97).

Culture and education

Normal cultural activity and suspending educational process has led to important changes. On one hand, there are more significant social inequities as families with high material possibilities will maintain education and cultural activities but for poor families, without financial and technological resources, educational process will be interrupted with possible regress, that is a major risk involving future generations as equal chances and eliminating poverty are important goals of every society (Venkatesh and Edirappuli 2020, 369). Moreover, developing psychological disorders in children affected by quarantine and isolation is another major risk. Education is a fundamental principle of every society and young people are maybe more vulnerable than adults in this case because the effect on them is a reflexion of the effect on the future of every community (Tyrrell and Williams 2020, 214).

Psychological impact of crisis

Every individual has a specific response to stress and its reflections to behaviour are particular for each of the exposed subject. There is a high chance that resources of adaptation and overcoming the crisis are not sufficient during a high-level global problem as an epidemic.

Some reactions are considered of normal intensity during such intense stimuli: fear of disease, fear and anxiety of certain symptoms apparently related to coronavirus, tendency to exaggerate protective measures, concern related to health care access, concern for family and loved ones, stigmatisation related to coronavirus infection or other health disabilities, anxiety, panic disorders, insomnia, somatisation or intensified anterior physical symptoms, withdrawal effects for nicotine, alcohol and drug users (Ornell, Schuch, Sordi, and Kessler 2020, 232-235).

There are also groups of individuals considered vulnerable during crisis such as elders, chronic somatic patients, children, chronic psychiatric patients and health care workers.

Psychological tension can be exacerbated and some events can have a direct impact over individual and an after-response in society. These circumstances can activate psychological problems even in healthy individuals: lack of family and social support, family members contacting the virus, deaths in close groups related to Covid-19, job loss, decreased professional activity, limited access to high performance health care, loneliness and disruption of normal relationships with friends and family. Mental health support has been introduced to all protocols in order to help and educate people into preserving their psychological comfort and balance (Fiorillo and Gorwood 2020, 63). The difficult part of the whole crisis is not necessarily the effects during crisis but the aftermath of the event. Prognostics on post-pandemic repercussions on mental health are probably more important than somatic health. Consequences can lead to other social network disruptions. Post-traumatic stress disorder is one pathology expected to outburst in the aftermath of the pandemics. Even healthy individuals could experience reminiscent anxiety, panic disorders, insomnia and difficulties in regaining normal social, professional and personal life. The human brain and even the human spiritual constitution are made to follow purposes and obtaining material and subjective goods. These functions are the main motivation for everyday life. Crisis reduces everyday motivation to one goal: survival, but disrupting routines and pleasant activities will lead to feelings of uselessness, depression, lack of purpose and meaning for life as the individual desires it making him vulnerable to find comfort in risk behaviours such as alcohol and drug abuse or compulsive eating with effects long after the crisis is over (Chen and Bonanno 2020, 51).

Conclusions

By this moment, the world and all countries are beginning to experience the first effects of the coronavirus pandemics. Society is hit at all levels, with disruptions in all its networks. But society unit of measure and construction factor is the human being, anchored in its matrix and working in group effort to build and maintain its balance. So the affected life quality of the individual will reflect in an uneven and inconstant affecting of social balance.

If we analyse the entire phenomenon that is currently in motion due to health crisis, chances are that consequences of this pandemic could be described as global social post-traumatic stress disorder. Vulnerability at all levels will persist long after the health issue will terminate and dealing with these consequences will create risk factors for political and economic dangers.

With the world already living with the “enemy”, it would be the right time to start worldwide cooperation for diagnostics, protocols and prevention of the mass social negative impact.

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